

HYDROCHLORIC ACID SOLUTIONS CONTAINING SILICA. PART I. CONDUCTIVITY AND TRANSPORT NUMBER MEASUREMENTS

BY HUSSEIN SADEK AND SASSON ABOUHAROUN

The conductance of acidified solutions containing low-molecular silica, having the same equivalent amount of alkali and the same amount of HCl, has been examined as a function of the silica concentration. As the silica content increases, the conductance drops accordingly. The effect is considered as being due to adsorption of ions. This view has been supported by transport number experiments which prove that silica acts as a non-electrolyte and that the transport number of the chloride ion in these solutions is lower by about 5% than the corresponding solutions, void of silica.

Lösenbeck (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1922, 16, 27) and Grundmann (*ibid.*, 1923, 18, 197) studied the reactions of silicic acid sols with acids in a quantitative manner by measuring the conductivity of mixtures of silicic acid and HCl, and the mobility of the colloid by transport number experiments. They found the conductivity of the mixture to be considerably smaller than the sum of the conductivities of both the components. Silicic acid, when added to HCl, lowers its conductivity below that of HCl alone. The lowering is greater, the higher the concentration of silica. The isoelectric point of the sol was found to lie at 0.001 N-HCl for a sol containing 0.099% SiO₂. If the reactions taking place down to the isoelectric point only involve the suppression of the ionisation of silicic acid, the decrease in the conductivity at the isoelectric point must be equal to the original conductivity of the sol. It amounts, however, to a multiple of this value. Lösenbeck conceives the combination with HCl in such a manner that the silica particles behave as a sponge which becomes gradually filled with HCl, the hydrogen ions being expelled with a certain solution pressure.

Moreover, Pauli and Valko (*Kolloid Z.*, 1926, 38, 289) studied the effect of addition of HCl to a well-defined sol, purified by electrodialysis. They showed that when the acid concentration was very low, the change in conductivity due to the binding was a time process. They assumed that after the isoelectric point had been overstepped, the silicic acid was undissociated. The decrease in the conductivity was explained as being due to the removal of HCl from solution in the form of the compound (SiO₂, HCl) through the formation of a basic chloride (SiO₂, H⁺) Cl⁻.

The aim of the present paper is to examine the binding process in the early stages of the ageing of the acid solutions containing low-molecular silica. The solutions were prepared by the addition of sodium silicate solution to hydrochloric acid while stirring (Sadek, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 507).

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium silicate solutions were prepared in such a manner as to contain the same equivalent of NaOH and varying amounts of silica. The ratios of Na₂O:SiO₂ in the silicate solutions were 1:1, 1:1.5, 1:2, 1:2.33. These solutions have been designated as silicate solution I, II, III and IV respectively. Pure silica was obtained by the disintegration of commercial water glass with HCl (conc.). The gel formed was washed repeatedly with distilled water till the chloride ion test was negative. The product

was then dried in an oven at 115° for several days. The dry silica was ground in an agate mortar to obtain a uniform powder. It was then analysed for its water content and impurities in the usual manner. The silica obtained was 89.55% pure. An exactly 0.100N-HCl solution was prepared from the constant boiling acid.

Conductance Measurements.—The resistance of acidified sodium silicate solutions was measured according to the classical method of the Wheatstone bridge. An audio-frequency oscillator producing 1000 cycles was used. The resistance readings were obtained for several fillings of the cell and were found to vary within 0.2%. The cell constant was 4.4288, as determined by potassium chloride using the data of Shedlovsky (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 1411).

Transport Number Experiments.—An apparatus similar to that used by Lottermoser and Fritche (*Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 80, 166) was employed.

FIG. 1

All parts of the apparatus were made of pyrex glass tubing of uniform bore, the inner diameter of which was 1.5 cm. A diagram of the apparatus is shown in Fig. 1. The anode compartment A is separated from the middle portion by a large stop-cock, T, having the same bore as the apparatus. The anode consisted of an amalgamated cadmium rod. The cathode, C, consisted of a pipe-form tube which was filled with pure mercury and covered with few crystals of copper sulphate. The capacity of the apparatus was 200 c.c. The total quantity of electricity was measured by means of a silver coulometer containing 20% silver nitrate solution. The apparatus was checked before use by filling it with 0.05 N-KCl solution. The transport number of the Cl^- ion was found to be 0.497 at 25° . This value is in good agreement with

0.501, found by Lottermoser and Fritche (*loc. cit.*) and with 0.490 found by Shemilt. Davies and Gordon (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1948, 16, 342).

TABLE I

Soln.	NaOH +HCl.	Soln. I. +HCl.	Soln. II +HCl.	Soln. III +HCl.	Soln. IV +HCl.
A { moles SiO_2 /litre 1000 κ	0.000 8.570	0.0221 8.476	0.0333 8.141	0.0443 8.067	0.0514 7.950
B { moles SiO_2 /litre 1000 κ	0.000 7.190	0.0233 6.974	0.0351 6.680	0.0466 6.542	0.0541 6.474
C { moles SiO_2 /litre 1000 κ	0.000 6.470	0.0240 6.237	0.0359 5.944	0.0480 5.859	0.0554 5.805
D { moles SiO_2 /litre 1000 κ	0.000 5.812	0.0245 5.578	0.0368 5.375	0.0490 5.401	0.0567 5.408

Solutions A, B, C and D were obtained by mixing exactly 20, 22, 23 and 24 c.c. of 0.1N-alkali respectively to 25 c.c. of 0.1N-HCl and the solution diluted to 50 c.c. in a standard measuring flask.

DISCUSSION

Table I and Fig. 2 show the change of conductance of four sets of solutions each of which contains the same equivalent of alkali and the same amount of HCl. It can

be readily seen that as the silica content increases, the conductance drops linearly. The curves run almost parallel to each other. The gradual drop in the conductance as the concentration of low-molecular silica increases could be explained on the basis of adsorption of conducting ions from solution. When these solutions were diluted, the conductance approached that of the corresponding acidified sodium hydroxide because of the break of the surface-adsorption complex. These findings indicate the surface combination of

HCl with silica and confirm earlier conclusions (Sadek, *loc. cit.*).

In order to elucidate the nature of the binding process, a comparison of the transport number of the Cl⁻ ion in these solutions with that in the corresponding acidified sodium hydroxide was carried out. The solutions were electrolysed for about 90 minutes. The results of a typical experiment on acidified sodium hydroxide is given below.

Original solution: 25 c.c. weighed 24.9926 g. and contained 0.03463 g. HCl, 0.06971 g. NaCl and 24.9194 g. H₂O.

Ag weighing 0.1383 g. was deposited corresponding to 0.04548 g. Cl⁻ ion forming 0.1176 g. CdCl₂.

Anode solution: All anode solutions weighed 55.4879 g. and contained 0.00283 g. HCl, 0.1299 g. NaCl, 0.1176 g. CdCl₂ and 55.2376 g. H₂O.

H₂O weighing 55.2376 g. should contain originally 0.1009 g. Cl⁻ ion. Cl⁻ ion migrating = 0.1270 - 0.1009 = 0.0261; hence

$$n_{cl^-} = \frac{0.0261}{0.04548} = 0.587.$$

Table II shows the results obtained with acidified sodium silicate solutions. It can be readily seen that silica does not move in the electric current behaving, thus, as a non-electrolyte. This result is expected if one bears in mind that silicic acid is a weak acid of the same strength as HCN or boric acid ($pK_1 = 9.7$).

The effect of non-electrolytes, such as sucrose, on the conductance and p_n value in aqueous HCl solutions was investigated by Zhukov and Dneprov (*J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1940, 10, 291). They found that the transport number of the Cl⁻ ion remained constant in solutions containing sucrose up to 30% by weight. Similar experiments by Fisher and Koval (*Univ. Kiev Bull. Sci. rec. chim.*, 1939, 4, 137) showed that sucrose, acetone and urea reduced the transport number of the H⁺ ion in aqueous sulphuric

acid solutions. These findings are not in agreement with those of Erdely-Gruz (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 131, 87) who found that the addition of 7.1% mannitol increased the transport number of the H^+ ion in HCl solutions in the concentration range 0.01–0.10 N. Also Harned and Dreby (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3113) observed an increase in the transport number of the H^+ ion in aqueous HCl solutions containing dioxane up to 20%.

TABLE II

Transport number of the Cl^- ion in acidified silicate solutions.

Original solution :	Soln. I +HCl.	Soln. II +HCl.	Soln. III +HCl	Soln. IV +HCl.
Wt. of 25 c c	24.9707	24.9744	25.0105	24.9965
Cl^- ion	0.04594	0.04610	0.04580	0.04584
HCl	0.00427	0.00525	0.00569	0.00558
NaCl	0.0689	0.06757	0.0664	0.0667
SiO_2	0.0358	0.0526	0.0651	0.0820
H_2O	24.8617	24.8490	24.8733	24.8422
Middle solution :				
Wt. of 25 c.c.	24.9721	24.9704	24.9967	24.9913
Cl^- ion	0.0460	0.0460	0.0458	0.0460
SiO_2	0.0360	0.0525	0.0649	0.0822
Ag deposited	0.1391	0.1460	0.1300	0.1304
Anode solution :				
Wt. of 25 c.c.	25.0191	25.0088	25.0123	25.0878
Cl^- ion	0.0534	0.0544	0.0545	0.0545
SiO_2	0.0355	0.0525	0.0647	0.0828
Anode soln.	73.8784	65.4618	68.3191	70.4956
HCl	0.0165	0.0106	0.0207	0.0291
NaCl	0.1642	0.1458	0.1405	0.1355
$CdCl_2$	0.1182	0.1241	0.1104	0.1108
SiO_2	0.1061	0.1416	0.1767	0.2334
H_2O	73.325	65.0640	67.971	69.987
n_{cl}^-	0.560	0.552	0.561	0.562

The results reported here indicate that the transport number of the Cl^- ion in the presence of 0.024–0.056 mole SiO_2 /litre is lower by about 5% than the value obtained in the corresponding solution, void of silica. The decrease in the conductance of the solutions with increasing concentration of silica could therefore be due to the decrease in the mobility of the Cl^- ions. The consequent increase in the mobility of the H^+ ions does not outweigh the decrease in the mobility of the Cl^- ions since the latter are more abundant in the solution.

However, Benton and Elton (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1953, **49**, 1213) showed that powdered silica dissolved in aqueous HCl solutions due to the formation of colloidal silica on the surface. The ξ -potential was found to amount to -90.5 mv. This result was obtained from conductivity measurements which indicated an increase upon the addition of silica. These results, although contradicting our findings, show that the process taking place with powdered silica is not necessarily the same as that with low-molecular silica. If silica is charged negatively in Benton and Elton's sense, it should migrate in the electric current, which is not the case. It seems quite probable that the dehydration of low-molecular silica in solution affects the adsorption energies of the H^+ and Cl^- ions in such a manner as to become equal. If this is true, low-molecular silica will adsorb H^+ as well as Cl^- ions with equal probability. This assumption lends itself to explain the fact that silica does not move in the electric current and that solutions containing low-molecular silica possess a lower conductance than the corresponding solutions of acidified sodium hydroxide.

ALEXANDRIA UNIVERSITY,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
ALEXANDRIA, EGYPT.

Received June 14, 1956.

[*Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Vol. **34**, No. 6, 1956]

HYDROCHLORIC ACID SOLUTIONS CONTAINING SILICA. PART II. POTENTIOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS

By HUSSEIN SADEK AND SASSON ABOUHAROUN

pCl measurements with the help of the silver chloride electrode were carried out at 25° on solutions containing low-molecular silica in the concentration range of 0.02–0.056 mole per litre. The results indicate that adsorption is taking place in these solutions. An equation has been developed which fits in with the experimental data. p_H values run in a parallel manner.

In an earlier communication by one of us (Sadek, this *Journal*, 1952, **29**, 507) pCl measurements on acidified sodium metasilicate solutions were reported. The results indicate a pronounced increase in pCl values over those calculated on the assumption that the Cl^- ions are totally free but nearer to those calculated on the basis of combination of one mole HCl per mole SiO_2 , and confirm the idea of compound formation between silica and HCl (Lösenbeck, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1922, **16**, 27; Tourky, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1939, **240**, 198). In Part I of this series (Sadek and Abouharoun, this *issue*, p. 443) it has been observed that silica behaves as a non-electrolyte and that adsorption of ions by low-molecular silica is responsible for the decrease on conductance and of the transport number of the Cl^- ion below the corresponding value in solutions, void of silica. If this view is correct, one should find an increase in p_H and pCl values as the concentration of silica increases in the the solution. In this communication potentiometric